

Payzullayeva Vazira Furkatovna,
Ochilov Uktam Saitkulovich
Shukurova Yulduz Kuchkor kizi,
Khalilova Nilufar Mamurzhonovna

*Siyab Abu Ali ibn Sina public health technical university
Samarkand, Uzbekistan*

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5882364>

TO STUDY THE PROCESS OF OBESITY IN THE HUMAN BODY

Annotation. *In recent years, interest in the problem of obesity has been growing everywhere. Obesity is a global, global problem. In developed european countries, 15-25% of the adult population is obese. All over the world, obesity is increasingly common in children and adolescents. In the same developed european countries, 25% of adolescents are overweight, and 15% are obese. Overweight of a child is a significant predictor of obesity in adults. More than 50% of children who are overweight at the age of six are obese in adulthood. As adults, 80% of obese adolescents will suffer from obesity [4, 9].*

Therefore, the problem of obesity is an increasing social threat to people's lives. It is relevant for everyone, regardless of gender and age, professional and social affiliation, place of residence. The significance of this problem is determined by the threat of disability of patients, a decrease in life expectancy due to the frequent development of concomitant diseases, which include hypertension, type II diabetes mellitus, atherosclerosis, coronary heart disease, dyspidemia, osteochondrosis, reproductive dysfunction, cholelithiasis. Obesity causes a decrease in resistance to infectious diseases, causes endocrine disorders, and dramatically increases the risk of complications during surgical interventions and injuries [6].

The purpose of the work: the development of obesity.

Tasks:

- consider the definition, epidemiology, etiology, pathogenesis, hospital, diagnosis, treatment of obesity;
- investigate the recovery and prognosis of obesity.

1. Definition of obesity

Obesity is a chronic multifactorial recurrent disease characterized by increased deposition of adipose tissue in the body (at least twenty percent in men, 30% of body weight in women, body mass index greater than 35-40 kg/m²) and progressing under the influence of physiological and genetic factors and environmental factors.

Most often, obesity appears with excessive consumption of high-calorie foods rich in fats and carbohydrates. This is primary, or alimentary, obesity, especially aggravated by low physical activity.

Obesity, which progresses in diseases of the endocrine glands and the central nervous system, is called secondary.

Obesity is a risk factor for the occurrence and development of diseases of the cardiovascular system (atherosclerosis, coronary artery disease, hypertension), and also complicates the course of diseases such as gallstone disease, diabetes mellitus, arthrosis and arthritis, functional disorders of the central nervous system [3

2. Epidemiology

Obesity is very common in the world. Women suffer from it more often (50%) than men (30%). Children are also susceptible to obesity (15-20%) [7].

In recent decades, there has been a tendency to increase the number of obese patients, which is associated with a decrease in physical activity at home and at work, as well as with the development of the food industry, which has led to cheaper food (especially rich in carbohydrates) and unbalanced excess nutrition. The increasing "rejuvenation" of obesity is a serious concern. A significant increase in the disease is observed at the age of 35-50 years. The mortality rate of obese patients is 60% higher than that of people with normal body weight.

The results of sample studies show that in Russia at least 30% of the population are overweight, and about 25% are obese [6, 12].

The number of overweight citizens is progressively increasing.

The European Society of Cardiologists and the European Society of Atherosclerosis indicate that, unfortunately, both patients and some doctors consider obesity to be an unsatisfactorily serious disease, underestimate the negative impact of excess weight on general well-being, especially on the human cardiovascular system.

The risk of developing type II diabetes mellitus increases significantly with obesity [8]. Two-thirds of obese people develop type II diabetes, and 90% of patients with type II diabetes are obese or overweight. According to the International Diabetes Federation (IDF), more than 50% of cases of type II diabetes could be prevented by obesity prevention. It has been shown that weight loss by 10% or more reduces the risk of developing type II diabetes by 44% [2, 11].

Epidemiological studies have shown that overweight people are more likely to suffer from diseases of the musculoskeletal system - osteochondrosis of the spine, metabolic and dystrophic polyarthritis, diseases of the hepatobiliary system - gallbladder dyskinesia, gallstone disease, chronic cholecystitis, tumor diseases of various localization, in particular, lung cancer, breast cancer, ovarian cancer and uterus. In women with obesity, menstrual-ovarian function is often disrupted and infertility develops [6].

Obesity is a risk factor for the development of thromboembolism and deep vein thrombosis.

Obesity is divided into four degrees:

I degree – body weight is 17-15% higher than normal;

II degree - excess of the norm by 25-38%;

III degree - excess of the norm by 60-100%

IV degree - exceeding the norm by more than 100%.

3. Etiology

Obesity is based on the interaction of genetic predisposition and external factors.

In 75% of children, the main cause of alimentary-constitutional obesity is considered to be a hereditary predisposition to excessive fat deposition [8].

It is difficult to influence a genetic defect and clinicians are currently focusing on external factors, which primarily include the nature of nutrition and the level of physical activity. To ensure energy balance, energy consumption should be equal to its costs.

It is necessary to note the importance of the nature of nutrition for the occurrence of obesity. It is known that the source of increased fat formation in the body are foods rich in carbohydrates (sugar, cereals, potatoes, etc.), as well as fats (butter, sour cream, cream, lard, etc.).

Age can also influence obesity. People aged 40-50 years are usually more prone to obesity than young people, due to significant changes in the body, leading to a violation of fat metabolism

Excessive deposition of fat in the body can be considered as an independent polyetiological disease, as well as as a syndrome in various other diseases [9].

Primary obesity in exogenous, constitutionally exogenous, hypothalamic, mixed forms and secondary obesity are distinguished, which develops as a symptom in syndrome complexes of pathological processes with lesions of the nervous or endocrine systems, with genetic diseases. More than 90% of all cases of the disease are primary obesity [13].

Factors leading to the development of obesity may be disturbances in the energy balance in the central nervous system at the level of the hypothalamus and overlying structures, morphological factors (increased number of fat cells in the body), functional factors (increased metabolic activity of adipocytes), some features of the adipose tissue itself, as well as a combination of factors. Obesity in parents and the severity of obesity in their children clearly correlate with each other [6]. Primary constitutionally exogenous obesity is associated with hereditary predisposition [9].

Various causes of obesity can be considered, but the main link in its occurrence and progression is always a positive energy balance. This is a situation when the energy intake into the body exceeds the consumption for a long time. The energy entering the body is equal to the caloric content of the food eaten. Energy is consumed to ensure the processes of basic metabolism, thermoregulation and provision of voluntary motor activity.

The more energy enters the body and the less it is consumed, the greater the energy imbalance. Excess, unclaimed energy by the body at the moment is deposited in reserve in the form of fat. Consequently, the leading causes of obesity are excessive caloric intake of food mainly due to food with a huge amount of fat and inactivity, or unsatisfactory motor activity. Fat deposits and excess weight can occur in a person with a low daily caloric content of food, but only if this person has even less energy consumption than consumption.

Patients who want to reduce body weight competently and painlessly for metabolic processes are recommended to keep a so-called Food diary, where all the food eaten during the day is recorded.

4. Pathogenesis

From a pathogenetic point of view, obesity is a consequence of a chronic energy imbalance. The development of energy imbalance is influenced by biological (including genetic), behavioral and environmental factors [8, 11, 12].

An energy imbalance is a mismatch between the number of calories coming from food and the energy expenditure of the body. Especially often this happens as a result of eating disorders: excessive intake of energy from food in comparison with energy consumption, good deviations in the ratio of nutrients from the accepted norms of reasonable nutrition (excessive consumption of fat food) or eating disorders — moving the main proportion of daily calorie intake of food to the evening hours. Excess energy coming from food in the form of triglycerides is deposited in adipocyte fat cells, causing an increase in their size and an increase in body weight.

Appetite is an emotional and faithful regulator of the amount of energy coming from food and the expenditure of this energy. In a healthy body, this regulation is carried out mechanically, but if the saturation centers (hypothalamus) are affected, this automatism is violated. As a result, a person consumes a huge amount of food and liquids, i.e. overeats. Obesity is progressing, as excessive intake of nutrients into the body leads to the fact that they turn into fats deposited in fat depots (the latter is monitored with a decrease in motor mode).

In real time, it has been established that the regulation of fat deposition and mobilization in the fat depot is carried out by a difficult neurohormonal mechanism,

including the cerebral cortex, subcortical formations, sympathetic and parasympathetic nervous systems, endocrine glands.

The fat metabolism is strongly affected by stress factors (cooling, overheating), organic lesions of the central nervous system, mental trauma, intoxication of the central nervous system, etc.

In particular, hormonal factors are of great importance in the stage of development of secondary or symptomatic obesity, due to the fact that the processes of mobilization and deposition of fat are narrowly related to the functional activity of most endocrine glands (especially the thyroid gland, adrenal glands, insular aggregate of the pancreas, gonads, pituitary gland).

Along with excessive fat deposition, violations of the function of different body systems are monitored.

Diseases such as atherosclerosis, hypertension, type II diabetes mellitus are considered in real time as natural complications of obesity. It has been established that their pathogenesis is based on the phenomenon of insulin resistance, that is, a decrease in the susceptibility of tissues to insulin.

The load on the heart increases due to the need to supply additional adipose tissue with blood. The contractility of the heart decreases as a result of fatty infiltration of the myocardium, mechanical compression of the heart by surrounding fat deposits.

A decrease in the mobility of the chest in obesity entails a decrease in pulmonary ventilation, and the high standing of the diaphragm, often monitored in obesity, reduces its excursion. All this increases congestion in the lungs, as a result of which gas exchange decreases and respiratory failure appears.

Excessive fat deposition in the abdominal cavity reduces the motor function of the intestine, which leads to disruption of other functions of the gastrointestinal tract.

The static load on the musculoskeletal system (joints of the lower extremities, spine) increases; as a consequence, arthrosis of the knee and hip joints, flat feet, osteochondrosis of the spine, herniated intervertebral discs appear.

Reduced motor activity, characteristic of obese patients, reduces performance, leads to changes in the functional state of the nervous system.

LIST OF LITERATURE:

1. Colditz GW, Wang, YC. Economic costs of obesity. In: Hu F, Obesity Epidemiology. New York: Oxford University Press, Inc., 2008.
2. Бугрова, С.А. От эпидемии ожирения к эпидемии сахарного диабета/ С.А. Бугрова// Медицинская панорама. – 2004. – № 4. – С. 15-21.
3. Васюкова, О.В. Инсулинорезистентность при ожирении у детей: спорность оценки/ О.В. Васюкова, А.В. Витебская// Проблемы эндокринологии. – 2009. – Т. 55, № 3. – С. 8-12.

4. Гинзбург М.М. Ожирение. Влияние на развитие метаболического синдрома. Профилактика и лечение/ М.М. Гинзбург, Н.Н. Крюков. – М.: Медпрофилактика-М, 2002. – 127 с.
5. Ogden, C. L., Carroll, M. D., Kit, B.K., & Flegal, K. M. (2012). Prevalence of obesity and trends in body mass index among U.S. children and adolescents, 1999-2010. *Journal of the American Medical Association*, 307(5), 483-490.
6. Данилова, Л.И. Феномен инсулинорезистентности в клинической практике: механизмы формирования и возможности коррекции/ Л.И. Данилова // *Лечебное дело*. – 2009. – №2 (6). – С. 29-40.
7. Дедов, И.И. Ожирение в подростковом возрасте. Результаты российского эпидемиологического исследования/ И.И. Дедов, Г.А. Мельниченко, С.А. Бутрова // *Терапевтический архив*. – 2007. – № 10. – С. 28.
8. Дедов И.И. Ожирение: этиология, патогенез, клинические аспекты / Под ред. И.И. Дедова, Г.А. Мельниченко. – М.: МИА, 2006. – 465 с.
9. Демидова, Т.Ю. Возможность повышения эффективности снижения массы тела у первично резистентных к фармакотерапии больных ожирением / Т.Ю. Демидова, Е.Л. Круглова// *Медицина критических состояний*. – 2009. – № 6. – С. 39-43.
10. “HEALTHY LIFESTYLES: Childhood Obesity: An Alarming Trend.”. *International Journal of Childbirth Education*, Smith, Elizabeth, March 2008. Santa Clara Univ. Lib. 2 March 2010.
11. Дубровский, В.И. Массаж: учебник / В.И. Дубровский. - М.: Владос, 2001. - 496 с.
12. Дубровский, В.И. Лечебная физкультура: учебник для студентов вузов / В.И. Дубровский. - М.: МИА, 2006. – 598 с.
13. Епифанов, В.А. Лечебная физкультура и спортивная медицина: учеб. для вузов / В.А. Епифанов - М.: ГЭОТАР-Медиа, 2007 - 568 с.
14. Проблема ожирения в Европейском регионе ВОЗ и стратегии ее решения/Под ред. F. Branca, H. Nikogosian, T. Lobstein. – ВОЗ, Европейское региональное бюро, 2009. – 408 с.
15. Toouli, J. Ожирение: Глобальные Практические Рекомендации Всемирной Гастроэнтерологической Организации/ J. Toouli, M. Fried, A.G. Khan, J. Garisch, R. Hunt, S. Fedail, D. Štimac, T. Lemair, J. Krabshuis. – *World Gastroenterology Organization*, 2009. – 42 с.

